

Geodesic Shape Distance and Integral Invariant Shape Features for Automatic Target Recognition

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Abstract

Scale, rotational, and translational invariance is important in shape classification problems for automatic target recognition. In this work, we employ integral invariant shape metrics and geodesic shape distance features for shape analysis of closed curves extracted from 2-D synthetic aperture sonar imagery. Results demonstrate that both metrics allow for good class separation over multiple target shapes whether through pair-wise comparison or with a small library of shape templates.

1. Introduction

The focus of this work is two-dimensional image analysis applied to synthetic aperture sonar (SAS) imagery, where the goal is to try to recognize objects in these images. The objects of interest are characterized on the basis of their features. There are two distinct types of image features that can be used for such classifications: shapes and textures. It is known, that the boundaries of objects in images characterize the objects themselves to a certain degree and, thus, the shapes of these boundaries become an important feature. Here, we will study the discriminating characteristics of two invariant shape metrics applied to the extracted boundaries of target objects.

Figure 1. Example target shapes from simulated SAS data. Clockwise from the top left, we have a block, a cone, a cylinder, and a sphere.

This research is guided by the need to automatically recognize targets of interest in static SAS imagery, and the fact that shapes of boundaries of these target objects can be

important in the process of discriminating between targets and non-targets. Figure 1 shows simulated SAS [6] imagery snippets of target objects.

2. Shape Features

There are various features that can be derived from shape that allow for a description of that shape, however these features may not possess scale, rotational, and translational invariance. The goal here is to classify shapes with the intent of eliminating these invariance limitations. Therefore, we will employ two invariant techniques, the integral invariant metric of [3] and the geodesic shape distance of [2]. Each method will be briefly described below, for a more in-depth discussion see [2], [3], and [4].

3. Integral Invariant Shape Metrics

Generally, shape invariants are defined via differential operations that are inherently sensitive to noise. As is shown in Figure 1, SAS imagery is rife with the potential for low SNR where the noise is background scattering. In [3] the authors introduced invariants which are defined as integral functions of the shape. These integral invariants are local descriptors, invariant to certain group transformations, and inherently robust to noise.

3.1. From Invariants to Shape Distances

Based on the integral invariants of [3], we define a shape distance metric between different shapes. Here, a meaningful shape matching, i.e. a dense correspondence mapping the parameterized domains of one shape to another, is critical, as distance is defined as the difference between the integral invariant values of corresponding points. This is found by minimizing an appropriate energy functional, whereby the optimal correspondence is computed which is affected both by differences in the local geometry of the two curves and by the amount of stretching or shrinking of the shapes' parameterization required to map similar points to each other.

Given this dense correspondence, the concepts of shape comparison, modeling, and interpolation can be naturally derived. One such integral invariant is computed by centering an isotropic kernel with a parameter r at a point p on the contour C .

We define $C: S^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ as a closed planar contour with infinitesimal arclength ds and G a group acting on $\mathbb{R}^2$, with

dx the area form on $\mathbb{R}^2$. We will also use the formal notation $\bar{C}$ to indicate the interior of the region bounded by C and μ is either the curve C itself or $\bar{C}$ with $d\mu(x)$ the corresponding measure, i.e., the area form dx or the infinitesimal arc length ds , respectively. The kernel is a 2D isotropic Gaussian with variance r or a ball B of radius r at a point p on the curve C . Then we define

$$I_C^r(p) \doteq \frac{\int_{\bar{C}} B_r(p, x) dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} B_r(p, x) dx} \quad (1)$$

as the normalized integral invariant area metric at a point p . Equation (1) represents the ratio of the inner contour ball area to the entire ball area. The range of this metric is $(0, 1)$, where a value approaching zero means maximal convexity and a value approaching one means maximal concavity. In this work we will use 2D isotropic Gaussians of radii 3-15 and take the correlated mean of the results as the distance.

Figure 2. Example Integral Invariant Metric Operation.

4. Geodesic Shape Distance

In [4] a novel representation of continuous, closed curves in $\mathbb{R}^n$ is presented for analyzing shapes. They combine the strengths of two important ideas - elastic shape metric and path-straightening methods - in shape analysis and present a fast algorithm for finding geodesics in shape spaces. The elastic metric allows for optimal matching of features while path-straightening provides geodesics between curves. Efficiency results from the fact that the elastic metric becomes the simple $\mathbb{L}^2$ metric in this representation.

For the interval $I \equiv [0, 2\pi]$, let $C: I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ be a curve with non-vanishing derivative everywhere. Denote its shape by the function $q: I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ as follows,

$$q(s) = \frac{\dot{C}(s)}{\sqrt{\|\dot{C}(s)\|}} \in \mathbb{R}^n. \quad (2)$$

Here, $s \in I$ and $\|\cdot\|$ is defined as the square root of the standard Euclidean inner product in $\mathbb{R}^2$. Then $\|q(s)\|$ represents the square-root of the instantaneous speed of the curve C . This function allows for the curve to stretch, shrink, and bend freely. This representation is then projected into the

shape space S of continuous, planar shapes. Given two reparameterizations q_1 and q_2 in S , the key is to find a geodesic between them. This is done using a path straightening approach whereby the given shapes are connected by an initial arbitrary path that is iteratively straightened so as to minimize its length. These iterations are performed using the gradient of an energy functional E until a critical point is reached. The resultant path is then the geodesic between these two shapes. This framework of elastic shape analysis and path-straightening is general enough to be applied to closed curves in $\mathbb{R}^n$.

5. Target Extraction

In order to analyze the shapes of the target objects they must be extracted from the imagery. There are several known methods for extracting objects from imagery, but they are not all meant to be used with SAS imagery. The shapes we are interested in are the shapes of the highlight regions of the targets. However, this could be employed to analyze the shapes of the shadow regions as well. In this work the Chan-Vese segmentation method combined with binary morphological processing will be used as off the shelf techniques. The algorithm will be briefly described below. The key here is that this method may not be optimal, but this is not the focus of this work.

5.1. Chan-Vese Segmentation

This is closely related to the classical Mumford-Shah functional [1], but uses a simple level set frame work for its implementation. The original Chan-Vese (C-V) algorithm will be presented below, however for more details see [1]. Defining the evolving curve C as the boundary of a region Ω , then, using the variational level set formulation with ϕ the level set function associated with Ω , the resulting model is

$$E(C_1, C_2, \phi) = \mu \cdot \text{Length}(C) + \nu \cdot \text{Area}(\text{inside}(C)) + \lambda_1 \int_{\text{inside}(C)} |\mu_0(\bar{x}) - C_1|^2 d\bar{x} + \lambda_2 \int_{\text{outside}(C)} |\mu_0(\bar{x}) - C_2|^2 d\bar{x} \quad (3)$$

where μ , ν , λ_1 , and λ_2 are all positive weights for the energy functional. Typically, $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 1$ and $\nu = 0$. An example of the C-V segmentation for the cylindrical target of Figure 3 is shown in Figure 4. It can be seen that the resultant segmentation is not connected and therefore results in multiple curves, rather than one curve as required here for shape analysis.

Figure 3. Example cylindrical shape SWAT image region of interest.

Figure 4. Extracted shape boundary result with the original Chan-Vese segmentation algorithm.

Therefore, an additional step is required to complete the boundary of the object. For this, a binary morphological image segmentation method is considered to improve upon the segmentation results of the C-V method.

5.2. Binary Morphological Segmentation

Morphology is a broad set of image processing operations that process images based on shapes. Morphological operations apply a structuring element to an input image, creating an output image of the same size. In a morphological operation, the value of each pixel in the output image is based on a comparison of the corresponding pixel in the input image with its neighbors. By choosing the size and shape of the neighborhood, you can construct a morphological operation that is sensitive to specific shapes in the input image.

The most basic morphological operations are dilation and erosion. Dilation adds pixels to the boundaries of objects in an image, while erosion removes pixels on object boundaries. The number of pixels added or removed from the objects in an image depends on the size and shape of the structuring element used to process the image. A structuring element defines the shape of the neighborhood mask that will be used for the morphological operation. Figure 5 shows the structuring element used here.

Figure 5. Binary image of the 21x21 diamond structuring element used here.

The dilation operation assigns the value of the output pixel to the maximum value of all the pixels in the input pixel's neighborhood, e.g. in a binary image, if any of the pixels is set to the value 1, the output pixel is set to 1. The erosion operation assigns the value of the output pixel to the minimum value of all the pixels in the input pixel's neighborhood, e.g. in a binary image, if any of the pixels is set to 0, the output pixel is set to 0. The morphological closing of an image is an operation that dilates an image and

then erodes the dilated image using the same structuring element for both operations. The algorithm for contour segmentation is as follows:

1. Run the C-V active contour method to extract a boundary of interest.
2. Convert this extracted boundary region in a binary image.
3. Close the binary image.
4. Fill the binary image holes.
5. Extract the boundary of the exterior contour of this filled region.

Figures 6 and 7 demonstrate the steps of boundary extraction described in the algorithm above.

Figure 6. Left, binary extracted region after the C-V method and right, the region of interest after closing and filling the binary result.

Figure 7. Extracted boundary of the enclosed region of interest.

As is shown, the boundary of the object of interest is extracted as a connected curve as opposed to the results with just the C-V method. This extraction algorithm was run for thirty images with four targets each at varying orientations resulting in 120 extracted targets. Figures 8 and 9 show two examples of each target class.

Figure 8. Extracted boundaries for block (left) and cone targets.

Figure 9. Extracted boundaries of cylindrical (left) and spherical targets.

6. Experiments

The aim of this work is to classify targets based on their shape features. Two such features are the mean integral invariant area and the geodesic distance. There are two

experiments that will test the ability of these features to resolve the targets. First, all 120 shapes are pair-wise distanced for both the integral invariant and the geodesic metrics. Second, all 120 shapes are pair-wise distanced with the six shape templates, shown in Figure 10 below, to get a baseline measuring stick rather than relying on the target set itself, since the dictionary of all shapes in a particular class may not be available in the field. The shape template measures will be clustered both independently and fused. A third experiment looks at the principal curvature components of each shape as an alternative feature. Whereby the shapes are projected onto the first three principle curvature components and clustered.

6.1. Shape Templates

The six templates below were chosen to represent ideal shapes that have various curvature features, i.e. right angles, arcs, etc. Therefore, we will measure the similarities between each targets shape and the six templates and then cluster these measures to look for groupings. To demonstrate the similarities and differences within the shape template group the pair-wise distances for each metric is shown in Tables I and II below. In addition, the scaled matrix images of the pair-wise metrics are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 10. Shape Prototypes-Bases: (1) Square, (2) Rectangle, (3) Cross, (4) Circle, (5) Triangle and (6) Bi-Triangle.

Figure 11. Left, Shape Template Pair-wise Integral Invariant Distance Matrix for r equal to 6. Right, Shape Template Pair-wise Geodesic Distance Matrix. Darker is smaller.

TABLE I. PAIR-WISE INTEGRAL INVARIANT METRIC RESULTS FOR THE PROTOTYPE SHAPES OF FIGURE 1.

	Square	Rectangle	Cross	Circle	Triangle	Bi-Triangle
Square	0	0.0161	0.022	0.0243	0.0119	0.0222
Rectangle	0.0161	0	0.0291	0.0282	0.0177	0.0233
Cross	0.022	0.0291	0	0.0416	0.0338	0.0407
Circle	0.0243	0.0282	0.0416	0	0.0302	0.0341
Triangle	0.0119	0.0177	0.0338	0.0302	0	0.0198
Bi-Triangle	0.0222	0.0233	0.0407	0.0341	0.0198	0

TABLE II. PAIR-WISE GEODESIC DISTANCE RESULTS FOR THE PROTOTYPE SHAPES OF FIGURE 1.

	Square	Rectangle	Cross	Circle	Triangle	Bi-Triangle
Square	0	0.321	0.6162	0.3848	0.4842	0.534
Rectangle	0.321	0	0.6743	0.4846	0.5934	0.5849
Cross	0.6162	0.6743	0	0.623	0.7408	0.7101
Circle	0.3848	0.4846	0.623	0	0.5927	0.801
Triangle	0.4842	0.5934	0.7408	0.5927	0	0.695
Bi-Triangle	0.534	0.5849	0.7101	0.801	0.695	0

7. Experimental Results

The target shape features are clustered for each of the experiments using their 3-D embeddings for two different manifold learning techniques, MDS and Diffusion Maps to demonstrate the discriminating ability of these two metrics. Figure 12 shows the results for the template-target pair-wise geodesic distance metric and Figure 13 shows the results for the template-target pair-wise integral invariant metric.

Figure 12. Shape clusters for template-target pair-wise geodesic distance metric, Diffusion Maps (left) and MDS (right). Red: Sphere, Blue: Block, Cyan: Cylinder, Yellow: Cone

Figure 13. Shape clusters for template-target pair-wise integral invariant distance metric, Diffusion Maps (left) and MDS (right). Red: Sphere, Blue: Block, Cyan: Cylinder, Yellow: Cone.

As can be seen in the clustering results above, the geodesic distance metric out performs the integral invariant metric for template-target pair-wise comparison. However, as is demonstrated in Figures 14 and 15 below the integral invariant produces better clustering results for these embedding techniques.

Figure 14. Shape clusters for target-target pair-wise geodesic distance metric, Diffusion Maps (left) and MDS (right). Red: Sphere, Blue: Block, Cyan: Cylinder, Yellow: Cone.

Figure 15. Shape clusters for target-target pair-wise integral invariant distance metric, Diffusion Maps (left) and MDS (right). Red: Sphere, Blue: Block, Cyan: Cylinder, Yellow: Cone.

In addition to the comparison of the two metrics, clustering was done using the fused features for template-target pair-wise distance metrics. The results of this are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Shape clusters for template-target pair-wise fused geodesic distance and integral invariant distance metric, Diffusion Maps (left) and MDS (right). Red: Sphere, Blue: Block, Cyan: Cylinder, Yellow: Cone.

As is shown, the clustering of template-target fused geodesic and integral invariant metrics compares well with the geodesic metric results in Figure 12.

The third experiment analyzes the principal curvature components of the shapes and the results of projecting onto the first three principal components. For the entire set of shapes the first nine principal components are shown in Figure 17. As can be seen, the first two components look similar to two of the shape classes, whereas the others resemble something else entirely. It must be noted that the components need not be non-intersecting curves themselves and that are just the principal curvature vectors for the shape

data. The plot in figure 18 show the clustering of shapes projected onto the first three principal components. The results demonstrate good separation for the eigen-curvature method. The major fallacy of this method is that a large sample of each shape size is required to calculate a reliable principal component decomposition that would capture a significant amount of the eigen-features relevant to each shape. Otherwise, the principal components may skew toward a particular class.

Figure 17. The first nine principal eigen-curves for the entire data set consisting of all four shape classes.

Figure 18. The clustering of shapes projected onto the first two principal curvature components. Red: Sphere, Blue: Block, Cyan: Cylinder, Yellow: Cone.

8. Conclusions

As has been shown, shape features can play a major role in distinguishing targets from each other. Both the distance metrics and the eigen-curvature method employed here offer discriminating information with regards to the shape classes; however, the next step is to demonstrate that these metrics can be used to discriminate targets from non-target as well. In addition to this extended non-target work, emphasis must be placed on the shape extraction algorithm to better provide the optimum representative contour for each object. Future work should also include other non-shape image features as well as non-image based features to fuse with the shape features to provide a multimodal object view that could enhance multiclass target discrimination in addition to target vs. non-target separability.

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10. References

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